

Commentary for *Vaccine*

Methodological Limitations in Meta-Research on Non-Specific Effects of Vaccines

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Introduction

In a recent commentary, Støvring et al selected 40 papers from Bandim Health Project (BHP) reporting results on randomized trials (RCTs) testing non-specific effects of vaccines (NSEs)[1]. The authors focused on 26/40 studies with trial-registration numbers on which they apply multiple testing procedures and Z-curve modeling to conclude that there is no evidence for NSEs in the BHP RCTs.

Given the public health relevance of NSEs, meta-research must apply statistical methods correctly and represent the underlying studies accurately. We argue here that Støvring et al's conclusion rests on fundamental problems. The commentary (A) misclassifies hundreds of tests as independent hypothesis tests, (B) applies statistical procedures under assumptions of independence that are not met, (C) interprets multiplicity-corrected results inconsistently, (D) uses an unsystematic selection of BHP studies, and (E) relies on undocumented *post-hoc* criteria introduced after publication. These issues materially affect the validity of Støvring et al's claim that BHP has produced no evidence for NSEs.

Misclassification of Hypotheses Tests

A central feature of Støvring et al's analysis is the treatment of numerous estimates as independent hypothesis tests. These include robustness checks, crude and adjusted models, intention-to-treat (ITT) and per-protocol (PP) analyses, and subgroup analyses, e.g., by age, sex, alternative time-windows, and interaction terms. Such estimates are not independent hypothesis tests. They are derived from the same population and therefore share data, design features, and sources of variability. Different model specifications do not create new hypotheses; they provide different estimates of the same hypothesis.

Multiplicity procedures are designed for multiple **distinct** hypotheses being tested in the same data. In direct violation of these principles, Støvring et al treat each test as a separate hypothesis and correct for all tests[2, 3] This artificially inflates the multiplicity-correction and the number of statistically significant results after correction becomes artificially low.

PaperID-18 in Støvring et al's commentary provides an example[4]. It is said to contribute 172 "tests" for a single secondary outcome (hospitalizations for infections). This number arises because crude and adjusted estimates are presented for ITT and PP analyses, across closely related subgroup analyses. These estimates are statistically dependent and conceptually linked. Multiplicity-correction across such highly correlated estimates will inevitably reduce statistical significance.

Erroneous Extraction of Hypotheses Tests

The total number of tests is repeatedly cited and forms the basis for multiplicity-correction and inferential conclusions. However, the commentary does not include extraction rules or classification criteria.

In a [request for retraction](#), we identified multiple errors in extraction, e.g., Støvring et al had counted reference group estimates (fixed at 1.00) and duplicate tests (estimates and corresponding p-values) as separate tests. In their [rebuttal](#), Støvring et al mention that "minor clerical errors" were corrected in Supplementary Tables S1 and S2. This wording is questionable. E.g., in PaperID-17 the total test counts changed from 80 to 160, and in PaperID-6 it changed from 210 to 168 following revision. The total number and the allocation of estimates and p-values, and the statistical classification of certain results, were changed in 13/40 and 8/26 studies in Supplementary Tables S1 and S2, respectively. This hardly qualifies as "minor clerical errors".

Surprisingly, Støvring et al have not changed a word in the commentary itself, though these reclassifications must have affected the numbers substantially. The commentary information remains insufficient for independent readers to reproduce these counts from the cited papers. A transparent framework would require explicit rules for identifying substantively distinct hypotheses, separating robustness checks from primary analyses, and specifying how tests are grouped into families for multiplicity adjustment.

Application of Z-Curve to Flawed Data and Under Violated Assumptions

Z-curves were designed to assess the distribution of significant test statistics. The methodology was developed and applied in psychology research characterized by many independent studies (at least 100), with a single result per study[5, 6]. Støvring et al apply Z-curve methodology on 23 papers which cover 13 RCTs. This extends the method beyond its operating context.

In their rebuttal, Støvring et al write "*We fully acknowledge that this analysis violates several formal assumptions underlying the z-curve analysis*". They then present a "paper-level" sensitivity analysis in which each paper contributes one statistically significant result (here they unexplained introduce a study, Biering-Sørensen et al, 2015, which was not part of their original analysis, but bears witness that data extraction is unclear and inconsistent). The paper-level analysis introduces a selection among results, which does not constitute a statistical criterion and is not auditable. Furthermore, the number of independent RCTs remains small, and expected replication rates are necessarily unstable.

Støvring et al furthermore argue that the Z-curve method is merely a "*supplementary descriptive diagnostics*" and that multiple procedures "*converge on the same qualitative pattern*". However, if

the data material has been extracted wrongly (see above), and all procedures rely on assumptions of independence, convergence across methods simply reflects propagation of flawed data material and the same violated assumption - rather than independent validation.

Inconsistency Between Numerical Results and Narrative Classification

Within the expanded multiplicity framework applied in Støvring et al's commentary, 8/26 studies were classified as having Holm–Bonferroni adjusted significant results in Table S2. Nonetheless, these same studies are described by Støvring as providing no support for NSEs.

PaperID-36 [7] (Table S2) illustrates this inconsistency. The RCT had two prespecified primary outcomes. One primary outcome – the all-cause mortality effect of measles vaccination in the presence vs. absence of maternal measles antibody - showed a highly significant result (HR=0.50, 95% CI 0.32–0.80, p=0.003) that remained significant after correction among the primary outcomes, and after multiplicity correction for all outcomes. Despite this, the study was classified as providing no evidence for NSEs.

Another example is PaperID-20. Though one of the 26 papers, it is simply not presented in Table S2. In this study, providing BCG and oral polio vaccine at the first home visit vs not providing it reduced the primary outcome, non-accidental early infant mortality, by 59% (8-82%)[9].

When statistically significant primary and multiplicity corrected outcomes are ignored or dismissed narratively, the interpretational framework lacks transparency.

Introduction of Post-Hoc Criteria

Following our request for retraction, Støvring produced revised versions of Tables S1 and S2 and materially altered the number of tests in 1/3 of studies. These changes profoundly modified the numerical inputs underlying the multiplicity correction and Z-curve analyses. In addition, new interpretational rules were introduced in rebuttal. Støvring et al introduce that when multiple primary outcomes were reported, only one - based on abstract-order - was counted. However, with multiple primary outcomes the conventional conservative approach is adjustment for multiplicity among outcomes rather than to select one and exclude others[10]. Selection based on abstract ordering is not a recognized statistical principle. Furthermore, Støvring et al write that secondary outcomes were evaluated only if “highlighted” by the original authors. However, multiplicity correction must correspond to the defined hypothesis. If correction is applied across a broad pool of tests, then **all** corrected results must be considered. One cannot have a test set that is based on the full paper, while narrowing interpretation to *post hoc* defined “highlighted” secondary outcomes. These *post hoc* criteria materially affect interpretation and limit reproducibility.

Inconsistent Selection of Papers

The selection of papers was not consistent. It is unclear how Støvring et al found 40 papers - BHP has >100 papers covering RCTs and NSEs – and how they end up only analyzing 26/40 papers (only 5/40 papers have no registration number). Some trials were represented by multiple papers including substudies. For other trials existing substudies were not included. Several BHP RCTs documenting NSEs were either not identified or excluded. For example, the RCTs of high-titer measles vaccine[11-13], that led WHO to withdraw the vaccine, were excluded because they were conducted prior to pre-registration being introduced.

Epistemological Context

Beyond these technical issues, the commentary reflects a particular epistemological stance.

Research on NSEs arises from prior epidemiological and immunological observations suggesting potential heterologous effects of vaccines which are context specific. In such contexts, excessive correction may increase the risk of overlooking real signals. As Rothman has argued[14], automatic adjustment for multiple comparisons is difficult to justify when studying biologically plausible relationships rather than random numbers. Multiplicity frameworks should be applied in light of biological context rather than mechanically in a statistical context.

Independent lines of evidence have clearly supported NSEs[15, 16]. The appropriate scientific question is not whether multiplicity corrections mathematically eliminate significance in individual tables, but whether the totality of evidence is coherently interpreted. There is no attempt by Støvring et al to assess the totality of evidence.

Conclusion

The commentary by Støvring et al treats sensitivity analyses as independent hypotheses, applies procedures under acknowledged assumption violations, base their interpretation on inconsistent data extraction and on inconsistent selection of papers; their rebuttal introduces post-hoc interpretational criteria not described in the commentary. These issues directly invalidate the central claim that there is “no evidence” for NSEs.

We hope that clarifying these methodological concerns contributes constructively to ongoing scientific discussion of NSEs and to rigorous standards for meta-research in vaccine science.

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